

A STUDY ON MULTI-CRITERIA DECISION-MAKING IN POWDER MIXED ELECTRIC DISCHARGE MACHINING CYLINDRICAL SHAPED PARTS

Tran Huu Danh

*Department of Mechanical Engineering
Vinh Long University of Technology Education
73 Nguyen Hue str., Ward 2, Vinh Long City, Vietnam, 85100*

Trieu Quy Huy

*Department of Mechanical Engineering
University of Economics – Technology for Industries
456 Minh Khai str., Vinh Tuy ward, Ha Noi, Vietnam, 11622*

Pham Duc Lam

*Department of Mechanical, Electrical, Electronic and Automotive Engineering
Nguyen Tat Thanh University
300A Nguyen Tat Thanh str., Ward 13, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam, 72820*

Nguyen Manh Cuong

Department of Mechanical Engineering¹

Hoang Xuan Tu

Department of Mechanical Engineering¹

Vu Ngoc Pi✉

*Department of Mechanical Engineering
Faculty of Mechanical Engineering¹
vungocpi@tnut.edu.vn*

¹Thai Nguyen University of Technology

666 3/2 str., Tichluong ward, Thainguyen City, Vietnam, 251750

✉ Corresponding author

Abstract

In life as well as in engineering, many times, it is necessary to choose the best option among many different options. That will be more difficult when the criteria given for the selection contradict each other. For example, when external cylindrical grinding, the minimum surface roughness requirement necessitates a small depth of cut and feed rate. The material removal rate will be reduced in this case, and this requirement will conflict with the maximum material removal rate requirement. To solve the above problem, a very useful tool is multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM). In this paper, for the first time, MCDM results for powder mixed discharge machining (PMEDM) cylindrical parts of SKD11 tool steel with copper electrodes have been presented. In this work, eighteen experiments with the L18 ($1^6 \times 5^3$) design using the Taguchi method were conducted. Six main input process parameters include the powder concentration, the pulse current, the servo voltage, the pulse on time, and the pulse off time. To select an alternative that simultaneously ensures two criteria including minimum surface roughness (RS) and maximum material removal speed (MRS), four different MCDM methods including MAIRCA (Multi-Attributive Ideal-Real Comparative Analysis), MARCOS (Measurement of Alternatives and Ranking according to Compromise Solution), TOPSIS (Technique for order of preference by similarity to ideal solution), and EAMR (Area-based Method of Ranking) and two methods of criteria weight calculation including MEREC (Method based on the Removal Effects of Criteria) and Entropy methods were selected. The results of MCDM when PMEDM SKD11 tool steel cylindrical parts with two methods for weight determination and four methods for solving MCDM problem were evaluated. In addition, the best alternative to ensure simultaneous minimum RS and maximum MRS was proposed.

Keywords: PMEDM, multi-criteria decision making, MAIRCA, MARCOS, TOPSIS, EARM.

DOI: 10.21303/2461-4262.2022.002367

1. Introduction

In the mechanical machining process, determining the appropriate process parameters plays a very important role in improving product quality, increasing productivity, as well as minimizing machining costs. The role of optimization is increasingly appreciated when it is necessary to machine high-strength materials (such as titanium, Inconel, and super-alloys) or parts with complex shapes. In this case, it also requires the application of non-traditional machining methods such as electrical discharge machining (EDM), wire-EDM, powder-mixed EDM or PMEDM, laser machining, abrasive waterjet machining, etc.

Most of the conventional optimization techniques, including the Design of Experiment Technique (such as Taguchi method, Response Surface Design Method, etc.) are based on gradient search. These techniques often have the ability to converge at the local optimal point, so they usually do not allow global optimization [1]. Therefore, they are not capable of solving MCDM problems where the criteria often contradict each other. In this case, it is necessary to apply MCDM methods for solving these problems.

MCDM is a problem to determine the best alternative among various ones. This problem has been extensively applied in various fields such as in medicine [2, 3], in transportation [4, 5], in military [6, 7], construction [8, 9], etc. In recent years, this problem has been applied to mechanical machining processes. It is well-suited to this field as a machining process often requires multiple criteria to be met simultaneously, such as maximum material removal rate (MMR), minimum surface roughness (SR), minimum processing cost, or maximum tool life. However, these criteria often contradict each other. Requiring a small value of SR will require reducing the depth of cut and the feed rate and as a result will reduce the MMR. Similarly, high MMR will require the increase of the depth of cut and increase of the feed rate. That will lead to an increase in SR and a decrease in tool life. Therefore, in this case, it is necessary to solve the MCDM problem to choose the best solution for a mechanical processing process.

Until now, many methods have been used to solve this problem for various machining processes. The MCDM problems have been solved for many machining processes such as turning [10, 11], milling [12], grinding [12], drilling [13, 14], EDM [15, 16], etc. Various MCDM methods such as TOPSIS [10, 11], DEAR (Data Envelopment Analysis based Ranking) [15, 17], MARCOS [11, 12], EARM [11], MAIRCA [11], etc., have been used to solve this problem.

PMEDM process is an EDM process where metal powder is added to the dielectric solution to overcome several limitations of EDM machining, such as small MMR and low machined surface quality. Like EDM, this type of machining is especially effective when processing recessed parts such as dies, and mold, and difficult-to-machine conductive materials. Therefore, research on optimization of PMEDM process as well as MCDM this process has been an interesting topic. The results of MCDM when PMEDM using titanium powder when processing SKD11 tool steel by using the Preferential Selection Index (PSI) method was reported in [18]. In this study, SR and MRR were selected as the criteria for this problem and a set of optimum input factors was proposed. The choice of the best option when machining Inconel 718 by PMEDM with titanium powder is outlined in [19]. In addition, the criteria given are also RS and MRR and the TOPSIS method was applied for MCDM. The TOPSIS method is also used when machining nickel free austenitic stainless steel by PMEDM with a dielectric solution mixed with nickel powder [20]. In this case, MRR, tool wear rate, and over cut were selected as criteria to select the best alternative. MCDM for the PMEDM process of mixing Si powder when applying TOPSIS method is also presented in [21] when machining EN-31 tool steel.

From the above analysis, it can be seen that there have been quite a few studies on MCDM for mechanical processing processes including PMEDM. However, studies on PMEDM are all done when machining parts in the form of concave faces or holes. In fact, EDM can be used for machining cylindrical shaped surfaces such as tablet shaped punches (**Fig. 1**) in the pharmaceutical industry, punches for steel stamping, as well as other profiled parts, etc. When machining these parts with EDM, the electrode must have the shape of a cylindrical hole. So far, there has been no research on MCDM when machining cylindrical shaped parts.

This paper presents the results of a study on MCDM in PMEDM when machining cylindrical shaped parts. In this study, the RS and the MRR were selected as the criteria for investigation.

These are the two most important output parameters and they are also the most popular subjects for optimization study of mechanical machining processes [1]. Also, four methods including TOPSIS, MARCOS, MAIRCA, and EAMR were used for MCDM and MEREC and Entropy methods was used to find the weight of criteria. MCDM results by different methods were evaluated. In addition, the best alternative to get simultaneous minimum RS and maximum MRS has been proposed.

Fig. 1. Tablet shape punches made by EDM process [22]

2. Materials and methods

In this work, four MCDM methods including TOPSIS, MARCOS, MAIRCA, and EAMR are used. In addition, two methods for calculating the weights of criteria, Entropy and MEREC, are used. In addition, the Taguchi method was used in this study to design an experiment for PMEDM when machining cylindrical shaped parts. This section describes the methods for solving the MCDM problem and calculating the weights of the criteria, as well as the design and setup of the experiment.

2. 1. Methods for multi-criteria decision making

2. 1. 1. Multi-Attributive Ideal-Real Comparative Analysis method

The MAIRCA method is used for MCDM following these steps [23]:

– Step 1. Forming the initial matrix by:

$$X = \begin{bmatrix} x_{11} & \cdots & x_{1n} \\ x_{21} & \cdots & x_{2n} \\ \vdots & \cdots & \vdots \\ x_{m1} & \cdots & x_{mn} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (1)$$

In which m is the alternative number; n is the number of criteria.

– Step 2. Defining preferences according to alternatives P_{A_j} . Assuming that the priority of the criteria is the same, it is determined by:

$$P_{A_j} = \frac{1}{m}, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, n. \quad (2)$$

– Step 3. Determining t_{pij} by:

$$t_{pij} = P_{A_j} \cdot w_j, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m; \quad j = 1, 2, \dots \quad (3)$$

In which, w_j is the weight of the criterion j .

– Step 4. Finding t_{rij} by the following equations:

$$t_{rij} = t_{pj} \cdot \left(\frac{x_{ij} - x_i^-}{x_i^+ - x_i^-} \right) \text{ if the criterion } j \text{ is as bigger as better;} \quad (4)$$

$$t_{rij} = t_{pj} \cdot \left(\frac{x_{ij} - x_i^+}{x_i^- - x_i^+} \right) \text{ if the criterion } j \text{ is as smaller as better.} \quad (5)$$

– Step 5. Determining g_{ij} by:

$$g_{ij} = t_{p_j} - t_{r_i}. \quad (6)$$

– Step 6. Calculating the final values (Q_i) by the following equation:

$$Q_i = \sum_{j=1}^m g_{ij}. \quad (7)$$

2. 1. 2. Measurement of Alternatives and Ranking according to Compromise Solution method

The MARCOS method is carried out in the following sequence [24]:

– Step 1. Proceed similarly to step 1 of the MAIRCA method.

– Step 2. Adding ideal (AI) and anti-ideal (AAI) solutions to the original decision-making matrix to create an expanded initial matrix:

$$X = \begin{matrix} & \begin{matrix} AAI & \begin{bmatrix} x_{aa1} & \cdots & x_{aan} \\ A_1 & x_{11} & \cdots & x_{1n} \\ A_2 & x_{21} & \cdots & x_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ A_m & x_{m1} & \cdots & x_{mn} \\ AI & x_{ai1} & \cdots & x_{ain} \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix} \\ X = & \end{matrix}, \quad (8)$$

wherein, $AAI = \min(x_{ij})$ and $AI = \max(x_{ij})$ if criterion j is as bigger as better; $AAI = \max(x_{ij})$ and $AI = \min(x_{ij})$ if criterion j is as smaller as better; $i = 1, 2, \dots, m; j = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

– Step 3. Normalizing the extended initial matrix (X). The elements of normalized matrix $N = [n_{ij}]_{m \times n}$ are found by:

$$n_{ij} = x_{AI} / x_{ij} \text{ if the criterion } j \text{ is as smaller as better;} \quad (9)$$

$$n_{ij} = x_{ij} / x_{AI} \text{ if criterion } j \text{ is as bigger as better.} \quad (10)$$

– Step 4. Finding the weighted normalized matrix $C = [c_{ij}]_{m \times n}$ by:

$$c_{ij} = n_{ij} \cdot w_j, \quad (11)$$

wherein, w_j is the weight of the criterion j .

– Step 5. Determining the utility degree of alternatives K_i^- and K_i^+ by:

$$K_i^- = S_i / S_{AAI}, \quad (12)$$

$$K_i^+ = S_i / S_{AI}, \quad (13)$$

where

$$S_i = \sum_{j=1}^m c_{ij}. \quad (14)$$

– Step 6. Determining the utility function of alternatives $f(K_i)$ by:

$$f(K_i) = \frac{K_i^+ + K_i^-}{1 + \frac{1 - f(K_i^+)}{f(K_i^+)} + \frac{1 - f(K_i^-)}{f(K_i^-)}}, \quad (15)$$

in which $f(K_i^-)$ and $f(K_i^+)$ are the utility functions related to the anti-ideal and the ideal solutions. These quantities can be found by:

$$f(K_i^-) = K_i^+ / (K_i^+ + K_i^i), \quad (16)$$

$$f(K_i^+) = K_i^- / (K_i^- + K_i^i). \quad (17)$$

– Step 7. Ranking the alternatives based on the final value of the utility function $f(K_i)$ to find the best alternative.

2. 1. 3. Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution method

The TOPSIS method can be carried out by the following steps [25]:

- Step 1. Creating the initial matrix as in the MAIRCA method.
- Step 2. Determining the normalized values k_{ij} by:

$$k_{ij} = x_{ij} / \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m x_{ij}^2}. \quad (18)$$

- Step 3. Finding the weighted normalized decision matrix by:

$$l_{ij} = w_j \times k_{ij}. \quad (19)$$

- Step 4. Determining the best alternative A^+ and the worst alternative A^- by:

$$A^+ = \{l_1^+, l_2^+, \dots, l_j^+, \dots, l_n^+\}, \quad (20)$$

$$A^- = \{l_1^-, l_2^-, \dots, l_j^-, \dots, l_n^-\}, \quad (21)$$

in which l_j^+ and l_j^- are the best and worst values of the j criterion ($j = 1, 2, \dots, n$).

- Step 5. Determining D_i^+ and D_i^- by:

$$D_i^+ = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (l_{ij} - l_j^+)^2}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m; \quad (22)$$

$$D_i^- = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (l_{ij} - l_j^-)^2}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m. \quad (23)$$

- Step 6. Determining ratios R_i by:

$$R_i = \frac{D_i^-}{D_i^- + D_i^+}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m; \quad 0 \leq R_i \leq 1. \quad (24)$$

- Step 7. Maximizing R to rank the order of alternatives.

2. 1. 4. Area-based method for ranking method

For applying the EAMR method for MCDM, the following steps need to be performed [26]:

- Step 1. Creating the decision matrix:

$$X_d = \begin{bmatrix} x_{11}^d & \dots & x_{1n}^d \\ x_{21}^d & \dots & x_{2n}^d \\ \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ x_{m1}^d & \dots & x_{mn}^d \end{bmatrix}, \quad (25)$$

wherein d is the index demonstrating the decision maker; $1 \leq d \leq k$ with k is the decision maker number.

– Step 2. Determining the alternative mean values for each criterion by:

$$\bar{x}_{ij} = \frac{1}{k} (x_{ij}^1 + x_{ij}^2 + \dots + x_{ij}^k), \quad (26)$$

in which k is the decision maker index.

– Step 3. Calculating the weights for the criteria.

– Step 4. Determining the average weighted value for each criterion by the following equation:

$$\bar{w}_j = (w_j^1 + w_j^2 + \dots + w_j^k) / k. \quad (27)$$

– Step 5. Finding n_{ij} values by:

$$n_{ij} = \bar{x}_{ij} / e_j, \quad (28)$$

where e_j is calculated by:

$$e_j = \max_{i \in \{1, \dots, m\}} (\bar{x}_{ij}). \quad (29)$$

– Step 6. Finding the normalized weight values by:

$$v_{ij} = n_{ij} \cdot \bar{w}_j. \quad (30)$$

– Step 7. Determining the normalized score of the criteria.

$$G_i^+ = v_{i1}^+ + v_{i2}^+ + \dots + v_{im}^+, \quad (31)$$

$$G_i^- = v_{i1}^- + v_{i2}^- + \dots + v_{im}^-. \quad (32)$$

– Step 8. Finding the ranking values (RV) from G_i^+ and G_i^- .

– Step 9. Determining the evaluation score of the alternatives by:

$$S_i = RV(G_i^+) / RV(G_i^-). \quad (33)$$

Ranking S_i to determine the best alternative (has the largest S_i).

2. 2. Methods for calculation of the weights of criteria

This section shows how to proceed with the MEREC and Entropy methods to determine the weights of the criteria.

2. 2. 1. Method based on the Removal Effects of Criteria

The MEREC method is a new criteria weighting method proposed recently in [27]. The steps to perform this method are as follows:

– Step 1. Creating the initial matrix as in the MAIRCA method.

– Step 2. Finding the normalized values by:

$$h_{ij} = \frac{\min x_{ij}}{x_{ij}} \text{ if the criterion } j \text{ is as bigger as better;} \quad (34)$$

$$h_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij}}{\max x_{ij}} \text{ if the criterion } j \text{ is as smaller as better.} \quad (35)$$

– Step 3. Calculating the alternative performance S_i by the following equation:

$$S_i = \ln \left[1 + \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_i |\ln(h_{ij})| \right) \right]. \quad (36)$$

– Step 4. Finding the performance of i^{th} alternative S'_{ij} by:

$$S'_{ij} = \ln \left[1 + \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{k, k \neq j} |\ln(h_{ij})| \right) \right]. \quad (37)$$

– Step 5. Determining the removal effect of the j^{th} criterion E_j by:

$$E_j = \sum_i |S'_{ij} - S_i|. \quad (38)$$

– Step 6. Calculating the weight of the criteria by:

$$w_j = \frac{E_j}{\sum_k E_k}. \quad (39)$$

2. 2. 2. The Entropy method

The Entropy method is a very popular weighting method. For applying this method, it is necessary to go through the following steps [28]:

– Step 1. Finding the normalized values of indicators.

$$p_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij}}{m + \sum_{i=1}^m x_{ij}^2}. \quad (40)$$

– Step 2. Calculating the Entropy value for each indicator.

$$me_j = -\sum_{i=1}^m [p_{ij} \times \ln(p_{ij})] - \left(1 - \sum_{i=1}^m p_{ij} \right) \times \ln \left(1 - \sum_{i=1}^m p_{ij} \right). \quad (41)$$

– Step 3. Determining the weight of each indicator.

$$w_j = \frac{1 - me_j}{\sum_{j=1}^m (1 - me_j)}. \quad (42)$$

2. 3. Experimental design and setup

To solve this MCDM problem, an experiment was carried out. The experiment was designed by using the Taguchi method with the design L18 orthogonal array ($1^6 \times 5^3$). The input factors and their levels were presented in **Table 1**. The experimental setup was described in **Fig. 2** with specification was shown in **Table 2**. After performing experiments, the SR (in this case is Ra (μm)) was measured and the MMS (g/h) was calculated. The experimental plan and the average values of the measurement results of RS and the calculation of the MRS (in triplicate) were shown in **Table 3**.

Table 1
Input factors

No.	Parameters	Code	Unit	Level					
				1	2	3	4	5	6
1	Powder concentration	C_p	g/l	0	2	3	4	5	6
2	Powder size	S_p	nm	100	500	1000	–	–	–
3	Pulse on time	T_{on}	μs	10	20	30	–	–	–
4	Pulse off time	T_{off}	μs	10	20	30	–	–	–
5	Peak current	IP	A	4	8	12	–	–	–
6	Servo voltage	SV	V	3	5	7	–	–	–

Fig. 2. Experimental setup

Table 2
Specification of the experimental setup

Parameters	Specification
EDM machine	EDM Sodick A30 (Japan)
Workpiece material	SKD11 tool steel
Electrode material	Copper
Mixed-powder material	SiC 100 nm
Dielectric fluid	Diel MS 7000
Surface roughness tester	Mitutoyo SV-3100

Table 3
Experimental plan and output results

No.	Input Parameters						Ra (μm)	MRS (g/h)
	C_p	S_p	T_{on}	T_{off}	I_p	SV		
1	0	100	10	10	4	3	1.940	9.877
2	0	500	20	20	8	5	2.485	16.098
3	0	1000	30	30	12	7	3.194	49.645
4	2	100	10	20	8	7	2.010	6.725
5	2	500	20	30	12	3	2.204	15.886
6	2	1000	30	10	4	5	1.239	41.983
7	3	100	20	10	12	5	2.309	32.487
8	3	500	30	20	4	7	1.126	12.425
9	3	1000	10	30	8	3	2.189	11.826
10	4	100	30	30	8	5	2.389	28.270
11	4	500	10	10	12	7	1.844	8.199
12	4	1000	20	20	4	3	1.031	5.289
13	5	100	20	30	4	7	1.850	5.329
14	5	500	30	10	8	3	2.335	15.200
15	5	1000	10	20	12	5	1.211	7.373
16	6	100	30	20	12	3	2.834	30.868
17	6	500	10	30	4	5	1.236	5.650
18	6	1000	20	10	8	7	2.572	5.293

3. Results and discussions

This section presents the results of study on MCDM using MAIRCA, MARCOS, TOPSIS and EAMR methods with finding the weights of criteria using MEREC and Entropy methods.

3. 1. Results of calculation of the weight of criteria using the Entropy and the MEREC method

The steps to calculate the weights of criteria using the MEREC method are as follows (Section 3.1.): calculating the normalized values using equations (34) and (35); Finding S_i and S'_{ij} according to (36) and (37). Then, determining the criterion removal efficiency using equation (38). Finally, calculating the weight of the criterion w_j according to equation (39). The results obtained are as follows: the weights of RS and MRR are 0.6603 and 0.3397, respectively.

The determination of the weight of criteria using the Entropy method can be done as follows (Section 2.2.2.): determining the normalized values p_{ij} by equation (40); Finding the Entropy value for each indicator me_j using equation (41). Finally, calculating the criterion weight w_j by equation (42) and the result is that the weights of Ra and MRS are 0.6872 and 0.3128, respectively.

3. 2. Results of multi-criteria decision making problem to find the best alternative in powder-mixed electric discharge machining

3. 2. 1. Results of multi-criteria decision making when using Multi-Attributive Ideal-Real Comparative Analysis method

The steps to apply the MAIRCA method to MCDM are as follows (Section 2.1.1.): Create the initial matrix according to equation (1). Then determine the priority of criterion P_{Aj} using equation (2). The value of parameter tp_{ij} is calculated according to (3). After that, calculate the values of tr_{ij} using formula (4) for MRR and (5) for SR. **Table 4** shows the values of t_{pij} and t_{rij} . Next, calculate g_{ij} using equation (6) and Q_i according to equation (7). **Table 5** presents several calculated results and ranking in MAIRCA method using the Entropy and MEREC methods to calculate the weights of criteria.

Table 4

Values of t_{pij} and t_{rij} in MAIRCA method

Trial	Entropy method				MEREC method			
	t_{pij}		t_{rij}		t_{pij}		t_{rij}	
	Ra	MRR	Ra	MRR	Ra	MRR	Ra	MRR
1	0.0429	0.0196	0.0249	0.0020	0.0367	0.0189	0.0213	0.0020
2	0.0429	0.0196	0.0141	0.0048	0.0367	0.0189	0.0120	0.0046
3	0.0429	0.0196	0.0000	0.0196	0.0367	0.0189	0.0000	0.0189
4	0.0429	0.0196	0.0235	0.0006	0.0367	0.0189	0.0201	0.0006
5	0.0429	0.0196	0.0197	0.0047	0.0367	0.0189	0.0168	0.0045
6	0.0429	0.0196	0.0388	0.0162	0.0367	0.0189	0.0332	0.0156
7	0.0429	0.0196	0.0176	0.0120	0.0367	0.0189	0.0150	0.0116
8	0.0429	0.0196	0.0411	0.0031	0.0367	0.0189	0.0351	0.0030
9	0.0429	0.0196	0.0200	0.0029	0.0367	0.0189	0.0170	0.0028
10	0.0429	0.0196	0.0160	0.0101	0.0367	0.0189	0.0137	0.0098
11	0.0429	0.0196	0.0268	0.0013	0.0367	0.0189	0.0229	0.0012
12	0.0429	0.0196	0.0429	0.0000	0.0367	0.0189	0.0367	0.0000
13	0.0429	0.0196	0.0267	0.0000	0.0367	0.0189	0.0228	0.0000
14	0.0429	0.0196	0.0170	0.0044	0.0367	0.0189	0.0146	0.0042
15	0.0429	0.0196	0.0394	0.0009	0.0367	0.0189	0.0336	0.0009
16	0.0429	0.0196	0.0071	0.0113	0.0367	0.0189	0.0061	0.0109
17	0.0429	0.0196	0.0389	0.0002	0.0367	0.0189	0.0332	0.0002
18	0.0429	0.0196	0.0124	0.0000	0.0367	0.0189	0.0105	0.0000

Table 5
Values of g_i and Q_i and ranking of alternatives in MAIRCA method

Trial	Entropy method				MEREC method			
	g_i		Q_i	Rank	g_i		Q_i	Rank
	Ra	MRR			Ra	MRR		
1	0.0180	0.0175	0.0356	8	0.0154	0.0169	0.0323	9
2	0.0289	0.0148	0.0437	16	0.0247	0.0143	0.0389	17
3	0.0429	0.0000	0.0429	15	0.0367	0.0000	0.0367	14
4	0.0194	0.0189	0.0384	12	0.0166	0.0183	0.0349	12
5	0.0233	0.0149	0.0382	11	0.0199	0.0144	0.0343	11
6	0.0041	0.0034	0.0075	1	0.0035	0.0033	0.0068	1
7	0.0254	0.0076	0.0329	6	0.0217	0.0073	0.0290	6
8	0.0019	0.0164	0.0183	2	0.0016	0.0158	0.0174	2
9	0.0230	0.0167	0.0397	13	0.0196	0.0161	0.0357	13
10	0.0270	0.0094	0.0364	10	0.0230	0.0091	0.0321	8
11	0.0161	0.0183	0.0344	7	0.0138	0.0176	0.0314	7
12	0.0000	0.0196	0.0196	3	0.0000	0.0189	0.0189	3
13	0.0163	0.0195	0.0358	9	0.0139	0.0189	0.0328	10
14	0.0259	0.0152	0.0411	14	0.0221	0.0147	0.0368	15
15	0.0036	0.0186	0.0222	4	0.0030	0.0180	0.0210	4
16	0.0358	0.0083	0.0441	17	0.0306	0.0080	0.0386	16
17	0.0041	0.0194	0.0235	5	0.0035	0.0187	0.0222	5
18	0.0306	0.0196	0.0501	18	0.0261	0.0189	0.0450	18

Table 5 shows that the MAIRCA method produced the best option 6 for both the Entropy and MEREC weighting methods.

3. 2. 2. Results of multi-criteria decision making when using Measurement of Alternatives and Ranking according to Compromise Solution method

According to the MARCOS method, MCDM is done according to the following steps: Calculating the ideal solution (AI) and the anti-ideal solution (AAI) according to (8). The calculated results of Ra and MRS are 1.031 (μm) and 49.6445 (g/h) with AI, and 3.194 (μm) and 5.2888 (g/h) with AAI. Calculating the normalized values of n_{ij} according to formulas (9) and (10) and the normalized values that take into account of the weight c_{ij} according to formula (11). The values of n_{ij} and c_{ij} are shown in **Table 6**.

Table 6
Values of of n_{ij} and c_{ij} in MARCOS method

Trial	Entropy method				MEREC method			
	n_{ij}		c_{ij}		n_{ij}		c_{ij}	
	Ra	MRR	Ra	MRR	Ra	MRR	Ra	MRR
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1	0.5314	0.1990	0.3652	0.0622	0.5314	0.1990	0.3509	0.0676
2	0.4149	0.3243	0.2851	0.1014	0.4149	0.3243	0.2740	0.1102
3	0.3228	1.0000	0.2218	0.3128	0.3228	1.0000	0.2131	0.3397
4	0.5130	0.1355	0.3525	0.0424	0.5130	0.1355	0.3387	0.0460
5	0.4679	0.3200	0.3215	0.1001	0.4679	0.3200	0.3089	0.1087

Continuation of Table 6

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
6	0.8321	0.8457	0.5718	0.2646	0.8321	0.8457	0.5494	0.2873
7	0.4464	0.6544	0.3068	0.2047	0.4464	0.6544	0.2948	0.2223
8	0.9159	0.2503	0.6294	0.0783	0.9159	0.2503	0.6047	0.0850
9	0.4711	0.2382	0.3237	0.0745	0.4711	0.2382	0.3110	0.0809
10	0.4316	0.5695	0.2966	0.1781	0.4316	0.5695	0.2849	0.1935
11	0.5592	0.1651	0.3843	0.0517	0.5592	0.1651	0.3692	0.0561
12	1.0000	0.1065	0.6872	0.0333	1.0000	0.1065	0.6603	0.0362
13	0.5572	0.1073	0.3829	0.0336	0.5572	0.1073	0.3679	0.0365
14	0.4415	0.3062	0.3034	0.0958	0.4415	0.3062	0.2915	0.1040
15	0.8516	0.1485	0.5852	0.0465	0.8516	0.1485	0.5623	0.0505
16	0.3638	0.6218	0.2500	0.1945	0.3638	0.6218	0.2402	0.2112
17	0.8344	0.1138	0.5734	0.0356	0.8344	0.1138	0.5509	0.0387
18	0.4009	0.1066	0.2755	0.0334	0.4009	0.1066	0.2647	0.0362

Next, calculate the coefficients K_i^- and K_i^+ using (12), (13). Determining $f(K_i^-)$ and $f(K_i^+)$ using equations (16) and (17) and the result is $f(K_i^-)=0.1434$ and $f(K_i^+)=0.8566$. Finally, determining $f(K_i)$ using (15). **Table 7** presents the values of $f(K_i^+)$, $f(K_i^-)$, $f(K_i)$ and ranking of the alternatives.

Table 7
Values of $f(K_i^+)$, $f(K_i^-)$, $f(K_i)$ and ranking of alternatives in MARCOS method

Trial	Entropy method				MEREC method			
	$f(K^+)$	$f(K^-)$	$f(K_i)$	Rank	$f(K^+)$	$f(K^-)$	$f(K_i)$	Rank
1	0.857	0.143	0.008	11	0.8566	0.1434	0.0081	11
2	0.857	0.143	0.007	17	0.8566	0.1434	0.0074	17
3	0.857	0.143	0.010	6	0.8566	0.1434	0.0107	6
4	0.857	0.143	0.008	16	0.8566	0.1434	0.0074	16
5	0.857	0.143	0.008	12	0.8566	0.1434	0.0080	12
6	0.857	0.143	0.016	1	0.8566	0.1434	0.0161	1
7	0.857	0.143	0.010	7	0.8566	0.1434	0.0100	7
8	0.857	0.143	0.014	3	0.8566	0.1434	0.0133	3
9	0.857	0.143	0.008	15	0.8566	0.1434	0.0076	15
10	0.857	0.143	0.009	8	0.8566	0.1434	0.0092	8
11	0.857	0.143	0.008	10	0.8566	0.1434	0.0082	10
12	0.857	0.143	0.014	2	0.8566	0.1434	0.0134	2
13	0.857	0.143	0.008	13	0.8566	0.1434	0.0078	13
14	0.857	0.143	0.008	14	0.8566	0.1434	0.0076	14
15	0.857	0.143	0.012	4	0.8566	0.1434	0.0118	4
16	0.857	0.143	0.009	9	0.8566	0.1434	0.0087	9
17	0.857	0.143	0.012	5	0.8566	0.1434	0.0114	5
18	0.857	0.143	0.006	18	0.8566	0.1434	0.0058	18

Table 7 shows that for both the Entropy and MEREC weighting methods, the MARCOS method produced the best option 6.

3. 2. 3. Results of multi-criteria decision making when using Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution method

The steps to perform MCDM using the TOPSIS method are as follows: Calculating the normalized values of k_{ij} according to (18); Calculating normalized weighted values l_{ij} according to (19). Then, determining the A^+ and A^- values of Ra and MRS according to equations (20) and (21). The values of k_{ij} and l_{ij} are presented in **Table 8**. Next, calculate the values D_i^+ and D_i^- according to (22) and (23). Finally, calculate the ratios R_i using formula (24). **Table 9** describes the values of D_i^+ , D_i^- , R_i , and ranks the alternatives according to the TOSIS method.

Table 9 shows that option 6 is the best for both Entropy and MEREC weighted methods.

Table 8

Converted and normalized matrix values in TOPSIS method

Trial	Entropy method				MEREC method			
	k_{ij}		l_{ij}		k_{ij}		l_{ij}	
	Ra	MRR	Ra	MRR	Ra	MRR	Ra	MRR
1	0.2310	0.1078	0.1588	0.0337	0.2310	0.1078	0.1525	0.0366
2	0.2959	0.1757	0.2033	0.0550	0.2959	0.1757	0.1954	0.0597
3	0.3804	0.5419	0.2614	0.1695	0.3804	0.5419	0.2512	0.1841
4	0.2393	0.0734	0.1645	0.0230	0.2393	0.0734	0.1580	0.0249
5	0.2624	0.1734	0.1803	0.0542	0.2624	0.1734	0.1733	0.0589
6	0.1476	0.4583	0.1014	0.1434	0.1476	0.4583	0.0974	0.1557
7	0.2750	0.3546	0.1890	0.1109	0.2750	0.3546	0.1816	0.1205
8	0.1341	0.1356	0.0921	0.0424	0.1341	0.1356	0.0885	0.0461
9	0.2607	0.1291	0.1791	0.0404	0.2607	0.1291	0.1721	0.0439
10	0.2845	0.3086	0.1955	0.0965	0.2845	0.3086	0.1879	0.1048
11	0.2196	0.0895	0.1509	0.0280	0.2196	0.0895	0.1450	0.0304
12	0.1228	0.0577	0.0844	0.0181	0.1228	0.0577	0.0811	0.0196
13	0.2204	0.0582	0.1514	0.0182	0.2204	0.0582	0.1455	0.0198
14	0.2781	0.1659	0.1911	0.0519	0.2781	0.1659	0.1836	0.0564
15	0.1442	0.0805	0.0991	0.0252	0.1442	0.0805	0.0952	0.0273
16	0.3375	0.3370	0.2319	0.1054	0.3375	0.3370	0.2228	0.1145
17	0.1472	0.0617	0.1011	0.0193	0.1472	0.0617	0.0972	0.0210
18	0.3063	0.0578	0.2105	0.0181	0.3063	0.0578	0.2022	0.0196

Table 9

Values of D_i^+ , D_i^- , R_i and ranking of alternatives

Trial	Entropy method				MEREC method			
	D_i^+	D_i^-	R_i	Rank	D_i^+	D_i^-	R_i	Rank
	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1	0.1548	0.1038	0.4014	10	0.1639	0.1001	0.3791	11
2	0.1652	0.0688	0.2940	17	0.1690	0.0687	0.2890	17
3	0.1770	0.1515	0.4611	7	0.1701	0.1645	0.4917	6
4	0.1670	0.0970	0.3675	13	0.1768	0.0933	0.3454	14
5	0.1500	0.0888	0.3718	12	0.1555	0.0872	0.3594	13
6	0.0312	0.2032	0.8669	1	0.0328	0.2053	0.8623	1
7	0.1199	0.1178	0.4955	6	0.1190	0.1225	0.5074	4
8	0.1273	0.1710	0.5732	2	0.1382	0.1648	0.5438	2
9	0.1602	0.0852	0.3474	15	0.1672	0.0827	0.3309	15
10	0.1330	0.1025	0.4352	8	0.1330	0.1062	0.4439	8

Continuation of Table 9

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
11	0.1564	0.1110	0.4150	9	0.1665	0.1067	0.3907	9
12	0.1515	0.1770	0.5389	3	0.1645	0.1701	0.5083	3
13	0.1655	0.1100	0.3992	11	0.1765	0.1057	0.3744	12
14	0.1588	0.0780	0.3293	16	0.1638	0.0769	0.3194	16
15	0.1451	0.1625	0.5282	4	0.1574	0.1561	0.4980	5
16	0.1609	0.0922	0.3643	14	0.1580	0.0990	0.3853	10
17	0.1512	0.1603	0.5146	5	0.1640	0.1540	0.4843	7
18	0.1971	0.0509	0.2053	18	0.2043	0.0489	0.1932	18

3. 2. 4. Results of multi-criteria decision making when using Area-based Method of Ranking method

To apply the EAMR method to solve the MCDM problem, it is necessary to follow these steps: creating the decision matrix according to formula (25) with the note that since there is only one result set, $k = 1$. Determining the mean of the alternatives for each criterion by (26) with the note that since k equals 1, $\bar{x}_{ij} = x_{ij}$. Next, determining the weights of criteria (Section 5.1). Calculating the average weighted values \bar{w}_j by (27). In this case since k is 1, $\bar{w} = w_j$. Then determining n_{ij} values by (28) with e_j defined by (29). Calculating v_{ij} using equation (30). The values of n_{ij} and v_{ij} are shown in **Table 10**. Determining G_i values using (31), (32). Finally, calculate the S_i value according to formula (33). The calculated results of G_i and S_i and ranking of alternatives by using the EAMR method are described in **Tables 10, 11**.

Table 10

Values of n_{ij} and v_{ij} in EAMR method

Trial	Entropy method				MEREC method			
	n_{ij}		v_{ij}		n_{ij}		v_{ij}	
	Ra	MRR	Ra	MRR	Ra	MRR	Ra	MRR
1	0.6074	0.1990	0.4174	0.0622	0.6074	0.1990	0.4010	0.0676
2	0.7779	0.3243	0.5346	0.1014	0.7779	0.3243	0.5136	0.1102
3	1.0000	1.0000	0.6872	0.3128	1.0000	1.0000	0.6603	0.3397
4	0.6292	0.1602	0.4324	0.0501	0.6292	0.1602	0.4154	0.0544
5	0.6899	0.3784	0.4741	0.1184	0.6899	0.3784	0.4555	0.1286
6	0.3879	1.0000	0.2666	0.3128	0.3879	1.0000	0.2561	0.3397
7	0.7230	1.0000	0.4968	0.3128	0.7230	1.0000	0.4774	0.3397
8	0.3524	0.4025	0.2422	0.1259	0.3524	0.4025	0.2327	0.1368
9	0.6852	0.3831	0.4709	0.1199	0.6852	0.3831	0.4524	0.1302
10	0.7480	0.9159	0.5140	0.2865	0.7480	0.9159	0.4938	0.3112
11	0.5772	0.2656	0.3967	0.0831	0.5772	0.2656	0.3811	0.0902
12	0.3228	0.1713	0.2218	0.0536	0.3228	0.1713	0.2131	0.0582
13	0.5793	0.1726	0.3981	0.0540	0.5793	0.1726	0.3825	0.0587
14	0.7312	0.4924	0.5024	0.1540	0.7312	0.4924	0.4828	0.1673
15	0.3790	0.2388	0.2605	0.0747	0.3790	0.2388	0.2503	0.0811
16	0.8873	1.0000	0.6097	0.3128	0.8873	1.0000	0.5858	0.3397
17	0.3869	1.0000	0.2658	0.3128	0.3869	1.0000	0.2554	0.3397
18	0.8053	1.0000	0.5533	0.3128	0.8053	1.0000	0.5317	0.3397

Table 11
Values of G_i , S_i and ranking of alternatives by EAMR method

Trial	Entropy method				MEREC method			
	G_i		S_i	Rank	G_i		S_i	Rank
	Ra	MRR			Ra	MRR		
1	0.417	0.062	0.149	16	0.4010	0.0676	0.1686	16
2	0.535	0.101	0.190	15	0.5136	0.1102	0.2145	15
3	0.687	0.313	0.455	8	0.6603	0.3397	0.5146	8
4	0.432	0.050	0.116	18	0.4154	0.0544	0.1310	18
5	0.474	0.118	0.250	12	0.4555	0.1286	0.2822	12
6	0.267	0.313	1.174	2	0.2561	0.3397	1.3265	2
7	0.497	0.313	0.630	3	0.4774	0.3397	0.7117	3
8	0.242	0.126	0.520	6	0.2327	0.1368	0.5877	6
9	0.471	0.120	0.255	11	0.4524	0.1302	0.2877	11
10	0.514	0.287	0.557	5	0.4938	0.3112	0.6301	5
11	0.397	0.083	0.209	14	0.3811	0.0902	0.2368	14
12	0.222	0.054	0.242	13	0.2131	0.0582	0.2731	13
13	0.398	0.054	0.136	17	0.3825	0.0587	0.1533	17
14	0.502	0.154	0.307	9	0.4828	0.1673	0.3465	9
15	0.260	0.075	0.287	10	0.2503	0.0811	0.3242	10
16	0.610	0.313	0.513	7	0.5858	0.3397	0.5799	7
17	0.266	0.313	1.177	1	0.2554	0.3397	1.3301	1
18	0.553	0.313	0.565	4	0.5317	0.3397	0.6390	4

It was discovered that the best option for both the Entropy and MEREC weighting methods when using the EAMR method is 17.

3. 2. 5. Results of finding the best experimental setup for powder-mixed electric discharge machining to achieve the lowest SR and highest MRR simultaneously

The ranking results of the alternatives when applying four MCDM methods including MAIRCA, MARCOS, TOPSIS and EAMR and two weight calculation methods (MERREC and Entropy) are described in **Table 12**. Besides, the results when using the four MCDM methods with the two weighting methods are also shown through **Fig. 3**. From these results, several comments are drawn as follows:

- using MAIRCA, MARCOS, TOPSIS, and EAMR methods with the weight calculation by MEREC and Entropy to perform MCDM will give different ranking results;

- the MAIRCA, MARCOS, and TOPSIS methods (except EAMR) all determine the same the best alternative (6), and that does not depend on whether the method used to calculate the criterion weight is MEREC or Entropy. Option 17 is the best according to the EAMR method. Meanwhile, the MAIRCA and MARCOS methods rank this option fifth and the TOPSIS method seventh, respectively. This result leads to the need to review the data in **Table 3**. From the table, option 17 in this table has $Ra = 1.236$ (m) and $MRS = 5.65$ (g/h). Furthermore, it is found that option 15 has $Ra = 1.211$ (m) and $MRS = 7.373$ (g/h). These data show that option 15 is better than option 17 because it has a lower Ra and a higher MRS than option 17. Since then, it has been demonstrated that the EAMR method did not identify the best experiment among the eighteen carried out experiments. From that, it can be said that the EAMR method may not suitable for the MCDM problem when PMEDM (at least for this case). This necessitates further research into the application of the aforementioned methods to other machining methods such as milling, grinding, EDM, and so on.

– option 6 is the best option. From that, to get the minimum SR and the maximum MRS simultaneously, the proposed optimum input factors are $C_p = 2$ (g/l); $S_p = 1000$ (nm); $T_{on} = 30$ (μ s); $T_{off} = 10$ (μ s); $IP = 4$ (A), and $SV = 5$ (V);

– MAIRCA, MARCOS, and TOPSIS methods can be used for MCDM when PMEDM. Also, the determination of the weight of criteria can be done using the MEREC method or the Entropy method.

Table 12

Ranking or alternatives when using MAIRCA, MARCOS, TOPSIS, and EAMR methods

Trial	MAIRCA		MARCOS		TOPSIS		EAMR	
	Entropy	MEREC	Entropy	MEREC	Entropy	MEREC	Entropy	MEREC
1	9	9	11	11	11	11	16	16
2	17	17	17	17	17	17	15	15
3	14	14	6	6	6	6	8	8
4	12	12	16	16	14	14	18	18
5	11	11	12	12	13	13	12	12
6	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	2
7	6	6	7	7	4	4	3	3
8	2	2	3	3	2	2	6	6
9	13	13	15	15	15	15	11	11
10	8	8	8	8	8	8	5	5
11	7	7	10	10	9	9	14	14
12	3	3	2	2	3	3	13	13
13	10	10	13	13	12	12	17	17
14	15	15	14	14	16	16	9	9
15	4	4	4	4	5	5	10	10
16	16	16	9	9	10	10	7	7
17	5	5	5	5	7	7	1	1
18	18	18	18	18	18	18	4	4

Fig. 3. Comparison graph of four multi-criteria decision making methods: *a* – entropy weight; *b* – method based on the Removal Effects of Criteria weight

4. Conclusions

This paper introduces the results of a MCDM study when PMEDM cylindrical shaped parts. From the findings of the study, several following conclusions can be given:

– in this work, four methods MAIRCA, MARCOS, TOPSIS, and EAMR have been applied to MCDM a PMEDM when processing cylindrical shaped parts;

- the MAIRCA, MARCOS, and TOPSIS methods are more effective than the EAMR method when PMEDM;
- with the MAIRCA, MARCOS, and TOPSIS methods, the determination of the best alternative does not depend on the MCDM method as well as the calculation method of the weight of criteria;
- for getting the minimum SR and the maximum MRS simultaneously when processing cylindrically shaped parts, the optimum input factors are $C_p = 2$ (g/l); $S_p = 1000$ (nm); $T_{on} = 30$ (μ s); $T_{off} = 10$ (μ s); $IP = 4$ (A), and $SV = 5$ (V).

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in relation to this paper, as well as the published research results, including the financial aspects of conducting the research, obtaining and using its results, as well as any non-financial personal relationships.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by Thai Nguyen University of Technology (Vietnam).

References

- [1] Zolpakar, N. A., Yasak, M. F., Pathak, S. (2021). A review: use of evolutionary algorithm for optimisation of machining parameters. *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, 115 (1), 31–47. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1007/s00170-021-07155-7>
- [2] Nobre, F. F., Trotta, L. T. F., Gomes, L. F. A. M. (1999). Multi-criteria decision making—an approach to setting priorities in health care. *Statistics in medicine*, 18 (23), 3345–3354. doi: [http://doi.org/10.1002/\(sici\)1097-0258\(19991215\)18:23<3345::aid-sim321>3.0.co;2-7](http://doi.org/10.1002/(sici)1097-0258(19991215)18:23<3345::aid-sim321>3.0.co;2-7)
- [3] Kou, G., Wu, W. (2014). Multi-criteria decision analysis for emergency medical service assessment. *Annals of Operations Research*, 223 (1), 239–254. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1007/s10479-014-1630-6>
- [4] Alkharabsheh, A., Moslem, S., Oubahman, L., Duleba, S. (2021). An integrated approach of multi-criteria decision-making and grey theory for evaluating urban public transportation systems. *Sustainability*, 13 (5), 2740. doi: <http://doi.org/10.3390/su13052740>
- [5] Aydın, S., Kahraman, C. (2014). Vehicle selection for public transportation using an integrated multi criteria decision making approach: A case of Ankara. *Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems*, 26 (5), 2467–2481. doi: <http://doi.org/10.3233/ifs-130917>
- [6] Wibowo, A. S., Permanasari, A. E., Fauziati, S. (2016). Combat aircraft effectiveness assessment using hybrid multi-criteria decision making methodology. 2016 2nd International Conference on Science and Technology-Computer (ICST). doi: <http://doi.org/10.1109/icstc.2016.7877358>
- [7] Petrović, I., Kankaraš, M. (2018). DEMATEL-AHP multi-criteria decision making model for the selection and evaluation of criteria for selecting an aircraft for the protection of air traffic. *Decision Making: Applications in Management and Engineering*, 1 (2), 93–110. doi: <http://doi.org/10.31181/dmame1802091p>
- [8] Temiz, I., Calis, G. (2017). Selection of construction equipment by using multi-criteria decision making methods. *Procedia Engineering*, 196, 286–293. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2017.07.201>
- [9] Antoniou, F., Aretoulis, G. N. (2018). Comparative analysis of multi-criteria decision making methods in choosing contract type for highway construction in Greece. *International journal of management and decision making*, 17 (1), 1–28. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1504/ijmdm.2018.10008499>
- [10] Trung, D. D. (2021). Application of TOPSIS and PIV methods for multi-criteria decision making in hard turning process. *Journal of Machine Engineering*, 21, (4), 57–71. doi: <http://doi.org/10.36897/jme/142599>
- [11] Trung, D., Thinh, H. (2021). A multi-criteria decision-making in turning process using the MAIRCA, EAMR, MARCOS and TOPSIS methods: A comparative study. *Advances in Production Engineering & Management*, 16 (4), 443–456. doi: <http://doi.org/10.14743/apem2021.4.412>
- [12] Do Trung, D. (2022). Multi-criteria decision making under the MARCOS method and the weighting methods: applied to milling, grinding and turning processes. *Manufacturing Review*, 9 (3). doi: <http://doi.org/10.1051/mfreview/2022003>
- [13] Tran, Q.-P., Nguyen V.-N., Huang, S.-C. (2020). Drilling process on CFRP: multi-criteria decision-making with entropy weight using grey-TOPSIS method. *Applied Sciences*, 10 (20), 7207. doi: <http://doi.org/10.3390/app10207207>
- [14] Varatharajulu, M., Duraiselvam, M., Kumar, M. B., Jayaprakash, G., Baskar, N. (2021). Multi criteria decision making through TOPSIS and COPRAS on drilling parameters of magnesium AZ91. *Journal of Magnesium and Alloys*. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.jma.2021.05.006>

- [15] Phan, N. H., Muthuramalingam, T., Minh, N. D., Van Duc, N. (2022). Enhancing surface morphology of machined SKD61 die steel in EDM process using DEAR approach based multi criteria decision making. *International Journal on Interactive Design and Manufacturing (IJIDeM)*, 16 (3), 1155–1161. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1007/s12008-022-00859-4>
- [16] Ray, A. (2015). A fuzzy multi-criteria decision-making model for green electrical discharge machining. *Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing*. Springer, 33–43. doi: http://doi.org/10.1007/978-81-322-2217-0_4
- [17] Huu Phan, N., Muthuramalingam, T. (2020). Multi Criteria Decision Making of Vibration Assisted EDM Process Parameters on Machining Silicon Steel Using Taguchi-DEAR Methodology. *Silicon*, 13 (6), 1879–1885. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1007/s12633-020-00573-4>
- [18] Huu-Phan, N., Tien-Long, B., Quang-Dung, L., Duc-Toan, N., Muthuramalingam, T. (2019). Multi-Criteria Decision Making Using Preferential Selection Index in Titanium based Die-Sinking PMEDM. *Journal of the Korean Society for Precision Engineering*, 36 (9), 793–802. doi: <http://doi.org/10.7736/kspe.2019.36.9.793>
- [19] Jayaraj, J., Sundaresan, R., Chinnamuthu, S. (2019). Multi-criteria decision of W-powder mixed electro discharge drilling parameters using TOPSIS approach. *Mechanics*, 25 (1), 52–56. doi: <http://doi.org/10.5755/j01.mech.25.1.22883>
- [20] Naik, D. K., Khan, A., Majumder, H., Garg, R. K. (2018). Experimental Investigation of the PMEDM of Nickel Free Austenitic Stainless Steel: A Promising Coronary Stent Material. *Silicon*, 11 (2), 899–907. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1007/s12633-018-9877-1>
- [21] Dewan, P., Pradhan, B. (2014). Parametric Optimization of Powder EDM Process using Grey Relational Analysis and TOPSIS. *International Journal of Applied Engineering Research and Development*, 4, 1–10.
- [22] Tran, T.-H., Nguyen, M.-C., Luu, A.-T., Do, T.-V., Le, T.-Q., Vu, T.-T. et. al. (2020). Electrical Discharge Machining with SiC Powder-Mixed Dielectric: An Effective Application in the Machining Process of Hardened 90CrSi Steel. *Machines*, 8 (3), 36. doi: <http://doi.org/10.3390/machines8030036>
- [23] Pamučar, D. V., L., Lukovac, V. (2014). Selection of railway level crossings for investing in security equipment using hybrid DEMATEL-MARICA model. *Proceedings of the XVI International Scientific-expert Conference on Railways, Railcon*. Niš, Serbia, 89–92.
- [24] Stević, Ž., Pamučar, D., Puška, A., Chatterjee, P. (2020). Sustainable supplier selection in healthcare industries using a new MCDM method: Measurement of alternatives and ranking according to Compromise solution (MARCOS). *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 140, 106231. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.cie.2019.106231>
- [25] Hwang, C.-L., Lai, Y.-J., Liu, T.-Y. (1993). A new approach for multiple objective decision making. *Computers & Operations Research*, 20 (8), 889–899. doi: [http://doi.org/10.1016/0305-0548\(93\)90109-v](http://doi.org/10.1016/0305-0548(93)90109-v)
- [26] Amiri, M., Antucheviciene, J. (2016). Evaluation by an area-based method of ranking interval type-2 fuzzy sets (EAMRIT-2F) for multi-criteria group decision-making. *Transformations in Business and Economics*, 15 (3 (39)), 76–95.
- [27] Keshavarz-Ghorabae, M. (2021). Assessment of distribution center locations using a multi-expert subjective-objective decision-making approach. *Scientific Reports*, 11 (1). doi: <http://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-98698-y>
- [28] Hieu, T. T., Thao, N. X., Thuy, L. (2019). Application of MOORA and COPRAS Models to Select Materials for Mushroom Cultivation. *Vietnam Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 17 (4), 32–2331.

Received date 09.04.2022

Accepted date 31.07.2022

Published date 30.09.2022

© The Author(s) 2022

This is an open access article
under the Creative Commons CC BY license

How to cite: Danh, T. H., Huy, T. Q., Lam, P. D., Cuong, N. M., Tu, H. X., Pi, V. N. (2022). A study on multi-criteria decision-making in powder mixed electric discharge machining cylindrical shaped parts. *EUREKA: Physics and Engineering*, 5, 123–139. doi: <http://doi.org/10.21303/2461-4262.2022.002367>